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Tax Sheltering Characteristics and Corporate Investment Expenditure in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study investigates tax sheltering characteristics and corporate investment expenditure in Nigeria. Using permanent book-tax difference and tax saving as proxy of tax sheltering characteristics with control variables such as operating cash flow (OPC), financial leverage (FLVR), and firm age (LFAGE) and total investment expenditure as proxy of corporate investment expenditure. The study used *ex-post facto* research design, data used were sourced from published annual report and accounts of the listed financial firms in Nigeria, covering the forty-nine (49) financial services firms in Nigeria as of that 31 December 2022. The study employed purposive sampling techniques, the selected ten (10) commercial banks, two (2) mortgage banks and eight firms from insurance and reinsurance sector that have complete data from 2012-2022. Using descriptive analysis, Pearson correlation, and other diagnostic tests such as, Stationarity and Cointegration, Heteroskedasticity, VIF, Serial Autocorrelation and Hausman Test and panel regression analysis as data analyses. The findings revealed that corporate investment expenditure does react significantly to the changes in the permanent book-tax difference of the listed financial firms in Nigeria while tax savings has a significant effect on the corporate investment expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria. Based on the analysis results the study recommends among others that, financial firms in Nigeria, should reduce the permanent book-tax difference in their books because it has been shown that as this gap is expanding, it adversely impacts business growth opportunities through corporate investment expenditure.

Keywords: Corporate investment expenditure, Financial leverage, Operating cash flow, Tax sheltering characteristics, Permanent Tax Difference, Tax Saving

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Tax sheltering comprises a wide range of acts with the express objective to lower tax (expenses) burden. (Dyrenge et al., 2016; Edwards et al., 2016; Gebhart, 2017; Ogbeide & Iyafekhe, 2018; Dyrenge & Maydew, 2018; Martinez et al., 2019, Obasi, et al., 2020, Anyaduba & Ogbeide, 2022; Delgado et al., 2023). In most of these research, the verb “reduce”, “minimize” “lessen” “lower” and “optimize” tax expenses were utilised. Tax sheltering is a legitimate activity as long as it is undertaken within the range of the law (Obasi et al. 2020). For an organization to implement efficient tax planning or sheltering practices, the managers must be knowledgeable in tax law and administration, audit and

have expertise. Kportorgbi et al. (2018) the managers must possess cognitive skills and personal dispositions. These skills include that the managers must be able to understand the tax legislation; discover (opportunity) gaps in the tax law, define consistent and successive plans to exploit the opportunities, and implement the scheme. Permanent book-tax difference (PTD) is the component of the book-tax difference (BTD) that reflects the difference between accounting profit (profit before tax) and fiscal profit (taxable income) caused by taxation provisions which do not have any future tax obligations (Sulistyowati & Hendrawati, 2018). PTD leads to permanent income gain or loss.

The financial firms are always seeking capital for investment expenditure to cope with their rapidly changing business environment. Currently, we are during rapid evolution in information technology where the survivability of any financial institution in this current hyper-competitive and highly dynamic business environment depends on the effective engagement of diverse resourceful electronic devices to support its service delivery (Igburu & Orife, 2024). Investment expenditure needs the acquisition of new assets and upkeep and improvement of existing ones to survive the test of time. Some spending categories which are put aside for investment upkeep are depreciation and amortization. While capital investment expenditure covers the cost of purchase of property, plant and equipment, the cost of acquisition of software or another tangible asset and so on. According to Adegbite and Shittu (2017), business investment is a key engine of economic growth in many economies and taxation has a large effect on a firm's investment decisions. However, the amount to which corporation taxation influences company investment is primarily an unsettled subject in economics (Moon, 2019, Igburu et al, 2023).

Generally, A huge number of the tax accounting literature has demonstrated considerable interest in the relationship between tax sheltering and business performance, cash flow, and firm value. However, the empirical evidence is not yet obvious. Also, the long-standing issue about the right level of book-tax compliance continues. The empirical results of the relationship between specific indicators of tax sheltering effective tax rate (ETR), the book-tax difference (BTD), the temporary book-tax difference (TBD) and permanent book-tax difference (PTB) and tax savings (TS) on the financial performance, firm value and cash flows are largely inconsistent. This contradiction is a pointer that the arguments have not been rested. In Nigeria, businesses are challenged with the issues of various taxations, ineffective administrative tax systems, high tax rates, unfriendly tax laws and other operating expenditures that endanger their survival and the going-concern status of their operations. Against this background the study is an attempt to answer this question by presenting empirical evidence from Nigeria financial services firm in examining tax sheltering characteristics proxy with permanent book-tax difference and tax saving as independent variables and corporate investment expenditure as dependent variable.

2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Permanent Tax Difference

Sulistyowati and Hendrawati (2018) define permanent tax difference (PTD) as the difference between accounting profit and fiscal profit generated by taxation provisions, and that accounting errors would have no impact on future tax liabilities. Permanent discrepancies arise when the difference between fiscal earnings and annual commercial profits does not recover in the future, resulting in variances in fiscal and commercial profits. They stated that recurring imbalances arise because of revenue and spending transactions being recognised according to accounting rather than fiscal, and vice versa. PTD results in permanent accounting net income loss or permanent taxable income gain (Igburu Et al, 2023; Sulistyowati & Hendrawati, 2018). Sulistyowati and Hendrawati (2018) suggested that PTD results from differences in revenue and expense recognition arrangements between traditional Financial Accounting Standards and Provisions and Tax Legislation, Regulations, and Guidelines. Empirically, Usman et al. (2020) investigated the relationship between corporate tax planning, board remuneration, and company value, as well as the role of board compensation in moderating any association between tax planning and firm value. The study looked at 71 profitable nonfinancial and non-oil and gas firms publicly listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) from 2008 to 2015. Using the generalised least squares (GLS) model, the data revealed a positive relationship between tax planning, board compensation, and firm value; however, board compensation did not attenuate the

relationship between tax planning and company value. Similarly, Olurankinse and Mamidu (2021) examined the relationship between tax planning and the financial performance of Nigeria's development banks from 2012 to 2019. The study used return on equity as a measure of financial success, effective tax rate and tax savings as explanatory variables, and capital intensity and firm size as controls. Data was analysed using multiple panel data OLS regression. The results show that the effect of effective tax rate and tax savings was statistically non-significant on return on equity, whereas capital-intensiveness and business size had a positive statistically significant influence on return on equity.

Tax Saving

The primary purpose of any tax sheltering, planning, avoidance, aggressiveness, or minimization activities, as they are referred to in research (Ogbeide & Iyafekhe, 2018), is to reduce tax expenses or burdens. As a result, the primary goal of the tax sheltering strategy is to save tax while remaining in conformity with the tax law. It represents the value of a corporation's or individual's tax decrease. Studies such as Ftouhi et al., (2016); Kawor and Kportorgbi (2014); and Obasi et al (2020) underlined that when a firm operates in multiple countries with various statutory rates, tax rate differentials can provide a tax benefit that is reflected in investment.

Empirically, Madugba et al. (2020) investigated the impact of tax savings behaviour on the size of Nigerian firms. The *ex-post facto* research design was used, with secondary data sourced from annual reports of firms registered on the Nigeria Stock Exchange. Descriptive statistics and panel data regression tests were conducted. The data were then subjected to a unit root test to determine their stationarity. The study found that interest tax savings and depreciation savings have a negative but significant relationship with firm size, whereas effective tax rates have a negative but negligible relationship. Similarly, Joseph et al. (2020) investigated the tax-saving behaviour of Nigerian firms to determine how it influences firm size. The *ex-post facto* research design was used, and secondary data were obtained from the annual reports of firms listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. Descriptive statistics and regression analysis were conducted. The study found that interest on tax savings and depreciation savings had a negative significant link with firm size, whereas effective tax rate has a negative but minor relationship with firm size.

Corporate Investment Expenditure

Business investment is the allocation of funds with the expectation of a future benefit. They believe that the influx of capital investments is influenced by a variety of factors such as taxation, legal and regulatory frameworks, and the degree of openness, among others (Osegbue et al, 2021). Corporate investment, according to them, is a driver of technological innovation, infrastructural development, wealth creation, employment and empowerment, and a rise in people's standard of living and social well-being in an economy. Consistent with this notion, Igbru et al, (2025). and Adegbite and Shittu (2017) found that corporate investment is one of the economic forces that encourages growth. Moon (2019), one of the most pressing economic concerns is the extent to which corporate taxes affect company investment. According to Adegbite and Shittu (2017), the sensitivity of corporate taxation to business investment varies depending on a country's tax laws, tax policies, and tax incentives, which is especially true in Nigeria, where taxation is being adjusted (Osegbue et al., 2021). Specifically, how tax-aggressive behaviours affect corporate investment behaviour is an important issue (Igbru et al, 2025).

Empirically, Obasi et al. (2020) investigated the impact of tax aggression on the corporate investment expenditures of 119 listed non-financial firms in the Nigeria exchange group between 2010 and 2017. The determinants of corporate tax aggressiveness examined in the study were tax savings, book tax gap, temporary tax disparities, and effective tax rate, with firm size serving as a control variable. Panel multiple regression was used in the analysis. The findings show that tax aggression has a statistically significant impact on corporate investment expenditure in Nigeria. Similarly, Ogunmakin et al. (2020) evaluated the relationship between tax evasion and the financial performance of listed firms in the Nigerian Exchange Group (NXG) from 2006 to 2014. The study looked at performance in terms of earnings per share, with profit before tax (PBT), debt-equity ratio (DER), and tax cost savings (COS) serving as independent factors. Multiple pooled ordinary least squares (OLS) were used to analyse the data. The findings indicate that tax cost savings had a negative but non-significant

relationship with profits per share, whereas the relationship between profit before tax and debt-equity ratio with earnings per share was positive and significant.

Theoretical Review

This study is anchored on Tax planning theory.

Tax Planning Theory

William proposed tax planning theory in 1961, claiming that taxpayers can organise their financial activities to incur the lowest possible tax burden through effective tax planning. According to him, not all tax strategies reduce the tax burden to the targeted minimum. He argues that not tailoring tax planning to individual taxpayers might lead to unfavourable tax outcomes. As a result, the assumption for effective tax planning includes proficiency in understanding tax law, the ability to identify opportunities in the prevailing tax law, the ability to devise a strategy to capitalise on the identified opportunities, and the ability to implement the strategy in the form of company policies. As a result, tax planning theory is critical to this work since it represents the skill level required for successful tax avoidance activities. According to Hoffman (1961) and Mgamal and Ismail (2015), tax planning activity theories generate ideas and philosophies that are generally applicable to tax practitioners. As a result, a tax plan cannot be permanent or continued for an extended period unless the tax planning acts are "flexible," implying tactic continuity. This is particularly relevant in cases when tax planning strategies rely on ambiguities and loopholes in tax legislation.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study employed an ex-post facto research design, as it enables the investigation of research problems using already existing data to derive empirical insights. Historical data were drawn from a population of forty-nine (49) financial services firms in Nigeria as of December 31, 2022. Covering the period from 2012 to 2022, the study selected firms with complete data across the eleven (11) years. Consequently, a sample of twenty firms met this criterion, comprising ten (10) commercial banks, two (2) mortgage banks, and eight firms from the insurance and reinsurance sector. Data analysis was conducted using descriptive statistics and panel regression techniques, facilitated by STATA version 14.2.

3.6 Model Specification

$$Y = \beta_o + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_nX_n + \mu_t \quad - \quad - \quad - \quad - \quad - \quad (3.1)$$

Using the present research variables, the model in equation 3.1 above is presented as follows:

$$TIE_t = \beta_o + \beta_1PTD_t + \beta_2TS_t + \mu_t \quad - \quad - \quad - \quad - \quad (3.2)$$

Where: TIE_t = Total Investment Expenditure at time t, β_o , = Constants, PBD_t = Permanent Book-tax Difference at time t, TBD_t = Tax Savings at time t, μ_t = Stochastic error associated with the model. $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_n$ = Coefficient of the independent variables in the model.

Introducing the control variables, the model in equation 3.2 above is presented as follows:

$$TIE_t = \beta_o + \beta_1PTD_t + \beta_2TS_t + \beta_3(OPC/TA)_t + \beta_4FLVR_t + \beta_5LnFAGE_t + \mu_t \quad - \quad (3.3)$$

Where: OPC/TA_t = Operating Cash Flow deflated by Total Assets at time t, $FLVR_t$ =Financial Leverage at time t, $LnFAGE_t$ = Natural Logarithm Firm age at time t. Other variables in the model

retain their original meaning. Robustness test will be carried out using New Investment Expenditure and Investment Maintenance Expenditure as the dependent variable. The model will be of the form:

$$NIE_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1PTD_t + \beta_2TS_t + \beta_3(OPC/TA)_t + \beta_4FLVR_t + \beta_5LnFAGE_t + \mu_t \quad -$$

(3.4)

$$IME_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1PTD_t + \beta_2TS_t + \beta_3(OPC/TA)_t + \beta_4FLVR_t + \beta_5LnFAGE_t + \mu_t \quad -$$

(3.5)

4.0 DATA ANALYSES AND INTERPRETATION

4.2.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics

<i>stats</i>	<i>tie</i>	<i>ime</i>	<i>pbd</i>	<i>ts</i>	<i>ocf</i>	<i>flvr</i>	<i>Infa</i>
Summary Stats							
Minimum	0.0102	0.0009	-4.0134	-0.0702	-0.1884	0.1277	0.0000
Maximum	0.4459	0.0468	1.6031	0.0446	0.4505	1.6616	4.654
Mean	0.0992	0.0066	-0.0826	0.0047	0.0429	0.6883	3.3209
Median	0.0559	0.0046	-0.0270	0.0037	0.0407	0.8143	3.3673
Standard Deviation (SD)	0.0977	0.0058	0.6868	0.0113	0.0890	0.2365	0.8127
SE(Mean)	0.0066	0.0004	0.0463	0.0008	0.0060	0.0159	0.0548
Normality Test							
Skewness	1.8793	3.5142	-2.5324	-0.7153	0.6922	0.4065	-1.5951
Pr(Skewness)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0001	0.0142	0.0000
Kurtosis	5.8621	21.8061	13.3668	13.3339	5.8443	3.3499	6.7422
Pr(Kurtosis)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.2357	0.0000
----- joint -----							
chi2(2)	64.1700	-	-	51.3500	27.7100	7.0200	59.4100
Prob>chi2	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0299	0.0000
Shapiro-Wilk W test (Prob>z)	0.0000						

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

Table 4.1 depicts the summary statistics conducted on the data. The “Overall” statistics are ordinary statistics that are based on 220 observations. The mean and the median of the seven variables, the powerful statistical measures of mid-point even though vulnerable to extreme values of the listed twenty financial firms in Nigeria in two hundred and twenty observations were computed. The closeness between the mean and median in almost all the variables particularly the explanatory variables suggest the existence of uniformity in the performance of the financial firms in Nigeria which indicates that the disparity in the sizes of the firms has no effect on their tax management performance, indicating no material extreme values. On the other hand, the standard deviation, a measure of dispersion, is not large suggesting that annual values of each of the variables are very close to the mid-point. These outcomes were supported by the quite small values of standard errors of the mean, the most valuable estimator, and conformed to the theoretical proposition of getting lesser as the sample size advances to the population. These variables recorded standard error values of less than 10% for all variables.

Also, normality tests were performed to determine whether a data set is modeled for normal distribution. Skewness is a measure of the asymmetry of the probability distribution of a random variable about its mean. In other words, it shows the amount and direction of skew (departure from horizontal symmetry). Although many statistical functions require that a distribution be normal or

nearly normal but if skewness is 0, the data are perfectly symmetrical. The skewness value can be positive or negative, or even undefined. Kurtosis explains the height and sharpness of the central peak, relative to that of a standard bell curve. Positive kurtosis portrays peakedness and heavy tails were as negative kurtosis show flatness and light tails, about the normal distribution. The null hypothesis of this test statistic states that the distribution is normal. Also, the decision rule is that the p-value of the test is greater than the significance level which in this case is 5%.

Pairwise Correlations

The Pearson correlation coefficients measure the degree of relationship between the different variables.

Table 4.2. Correlation Matrix with P-values involving 220 Observations

	<i>tie</i>	<i>ime</i>	<i>pbd</i>	<i>ts</i>	<i>ocf</i>	<i>flvr</i>	<i>Infa</i>
<i>tie</i>	1.0000						
<i>ime</i>	0.7190*	1.0000					
	0.0000						
<i>pbd</i>	0.1790*	0.2901*	1.0000				
	0.0078	0.0000					
<i>ts</i>	0.0245	-0.0091	0.0852	1.0000			
	0.7173	0.8927	0.2082				
<i>ocf</i>	-0.1923*	-0.0806	0.0091	0.1076	1.0000		
	0.0042	0.2339	0.8928	0.1116			
<i>flvr</i>	-0.7467*	-0.6223*	0.2892*	-0.1349*	0.1403*	1.0000	
	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0456	0.0376		
<i>Infa</i>	0.1695*	0.2247*	-0.2577*	0.0210	-0.0612	0.1225	1.0000
	0.0118	0.0008	0.0001	0.7566	0.3662	0.0697	

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

Table 4.2 portrays a significant relationship between five (5) predictor variables (temporary book tax difference, permanent book tax difference, operating cash flows all deflated by total assets financial leverage and natural logarithm of firm age and total investment expenditure of listed financial firms in Nigeria. Precisely, permanent book tax and the natural logarithm of firm age exhibited a strong positive relationship with investment expenditure. However, the relationship between the investment maintenance expenditure and tax savings and operating cash flows are non-significant.

Diagnostic Tests for Stationarity and Cointegration

Unit roots are one cause of non-stationarity. Unit roots test is a test for stationarity in a time series. A time series has stationarity if a shift in time doesn't cause a change in the shape of the distribution; that means that the time series has a constant meaning and constant variance over time (Choi, 2001). This test is particularly important for the calculation of reliable test statistics and, hence, can have a significant impact on model selection. We conducted the Levin-Lin Chu unit-root test given that our dataset is balanced with $N > T$. The null hypothesis of the Levin-Lin Chu unit-root test states that panels contain unit roots.

Ho: Panels contain unit roots	Number of panels = 20
Ha: Panels are stationary	Number of periods = 11
AR parameter: Common	Asymptotics: N/T -> 0
Panel means: Included	ADF regressions: 1-3 lag
Time trend: Included	

Table 4.3 Levin-Lin-Chu unit-root test Based on Based on Augmented Dickey-Fuller tests

Variables	Unadjusted t	Adjusted t*	p-value	Lags
	<i>Statistics</i>	<i>Statistics</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>ADF regressions</i>
Tie	-24.8551	-18.7304	0.0000	3
lme	-11.8000	-4.0483	0.0001	1
Etr	-16.0771	-10.6635	0.0153	3
Btd	-20.9004	-15.8683	0.0000	1
Tbd	-9.0744	-6.9029	0.0000	1
Pbd	-14.4381	-9.9187	0.0000	1
Ts	-20.8964	-15.8616	0.0000	1
Ocf	-15.5848	-8.4760	0.0000	1
Flvr	-36.2706	-33.5206	0.0000	3
Lnage	-14.1844	-11.2943	0.0000	1

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

Table 4.4 depicts the outcome of the Levin-Lin Chu unit-root test based on augmented Dickey-Fuller tests carried out on data at lag 1 to 3. The results of this test statistics strongly reject the null hypothesis that the panels contain unit-roots for all the entered variables at lag 1-3. Therefore, we conclude that the data for all variables in the study are stationary.

Diagnostic Test for Heteroskedasticity

Table 4.4: Breusch-Pagan Test for Heteroskedasticity (All-Inclusive Model)

Ho: Constant variance			
Variables: fitted values of	tieta	tieta	imeta
chi2(1)	=	116.74	207.47
Prob > chi2	=	0.0000	0.0000

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

Table 4.8 depicts the Breusch-Pagan test result for heteroskedasticity for the model specification. Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test was employed to ascertain whether the standard deviation of the data over the period is statistically constant (heteroskedasticity problem). Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test assumes the p-value of above the significant levels to be free from heteroskedasticity problem among the datasets. In this case, the result shows a Prob>chi2 = 0.0000 which is very significant. This result signifies the presence of a heteroskedasticity problem on the dataset. If this is not corrected, it leads to biased standard errors. It was controlled employing the robust command while regressing to arrive at robust standard errors (Montgomery & Peck, 2007).

Table 4.5: Variance Inflation Factor

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
btd	10.58	0.000004
tbd	8.23	0.000004
pbd	5.77	0.452926
tbd	5.73	0.513138
flvr	1.21	0.825739
lnfa	1.14	0.877631
etr	1.08	0.924181
ocf	1.06	0.944081
Mean VIF		4.35

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

A test of multicollinearity was conducted using the variance inflation factor approach (VIF) as depicted in Table 4.7. In this instance, the explanatory variables have resultant variance inflation

factors ranging between 1.06 and 10.58 and a mean VIF of $4.35 < 5.0$ for the comprehensive model. These results indicate the presence of severe multicollinearity problems connected to book tax difference deflated by the total assets and tax savings to total assets but moderate multicollinearity between the explanatory (independent) variables in the regression model which is acceptable. Nonetheless, in case of severe multicollinearity problem, Gujarati and Porter (2009) posit that it is likely to be resolved by removing one or more variables, employing a priori information from theory, transforming variables, adding new data, and principal components analysis or by employing factor analysis and ridge regression among others.

Table 4.8: Wooldridge test (All-Inclusive Model)

Wooldridge test for autocorrelation in panel data			
Ho: no first-order autocorrelation			
F(1, 7)	=	93.064	1845.54
Prob > F	=	0.0000	0.0000

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

Further, the Wooldridge tests of serial autocorrelation in panel data were carried out. The Wooldridge tests assumed a null hypothesis of no first-order autocorrelation. In this instance, Table 4.8 depicts the outcome of the test. The result reveals a non-significant p-value ($\text{Prob} > F = 0.0000$) which is less than 0.05 significant levels indicating that the panel data is not free from first-order autocorrelation. **Hence, we upheld the alternative hypothesis.** Nevertheless, it was resolved by conducting a regression model that adjusted for first-order autocorrelation (ar1).

Diagnostic of Test for Heteroskedasticity in Panel Data

4.9. Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian Multiplier test for Random effects

	Var	sd = sqrt(Var)
Tieta	.0095529	.0977389
E	.0010871	.0329716
U	.0010849	.0329376

Test: $\text{Var}(u) = 0$

chibar2 (01) =	340.80
Prob > chibar2 =	0.0000

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

The Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian Multiplier test doubles as the test for the presence of panel heteroskedasticity and test to facilitate the decision between the *Random Effects Model (REM)* and the *Pooled Ordinary Least Square (POLS)*. The Breusch-Pagan Lagrange multiplier (LM) test has the *null hypothesis that variances across entities are zero* which means no statistically significant difference across units (no panel effect). The decision rule is that if the Breusch Pagan Lagrange Multiplier (LM) result is significant at 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis will be rejected. As depicted in table 4.9, the result of this test shows $\chi^2(1) = 340.80$ and $\text{Prob} > \text{chibar}^2 = 0.0000$. The result shows the null hypothesis is rejected as it is strongly significant at the 5% level of significance, which implies that the random effect model is appropriate for the model estimation. **Therefore, we have decided that the Random Effect Model (REM) is better.** Again, these results also provide evidence of heteroskedasticity problems in the panel data. In this case, we therefore, reject the null hypothesis of the test is homoscedasticity and conclude that the panel dataset has heteroskedasticity problems. However, this problem was controlled by adopting a robust regression model that checked the panel-level heteroskedasticity.

Fixed Effects Vs Random Effects Tests of Model Estimation

Table 4.10: Hausman Test of All-Inclusive Model Validity

Variable	(b) fe	(B) Re	(b-B) Difference	sqrt(diag(V_b- V_B)) S.E.
etr	-0.005144	-0.006203	0.001059	0.045259
btd	-3.455404	4.031168	-7.486572	0.163525
tbd	-110.1463	-142.2445	32.09825	0.019358
pbd	-11.02241	-14.22521	3.202798	0.045436
ts	47.92244	33.61028	14.31216	0.405522
ocf	0.0281372	0.0235908	0.0045464	0.030029
flvr	-0.0771574	-0.1616139	0.0844565	0.0059191
lnfa	-0.0160179	-0.0001993	-0.0158186	0.0040423

b = consistent under Ho and Ha; obtained from xtreg

B = inconsistent under Ha, efficient under Ho; obtained from xtreg

Test: Ho: difference in coefficients not systematic

$$\chi^2(8) = (b-B)'[(V_b-V_B)^{-1}](b-B) = 129.44$$

$$\text{Prob}>\chi^2 = 0.0000$$

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

Table 4.10 facilitates a choice between the *Fixed Effects Model (FEM)* and the *Random Effects Model (REM)*. The Hausman test has the null hypothesis that the preferred model is fixed effects vs the alternative fixed effect. The Hausman test results show $\chi^2(8) = 129.44$ and $\text{Prob.}>\chi^2 = 0.0000$ which suggest that the fixed effect model is not appropriate therefore strengthens the decision that the *Random Effect Model (REM)* is the most appropriate model for the panel dataset.

Table 4.11: Panel Regression Results of Tax Sheltering Indicators, Control Variables and Corporate Investment Expenditure of Listed Financial firms in Nigeria

Regressors		Method	Pooled OLS	Fixed Effect	Random Effect (Recommended Model)	PCSEs (Preferred Model)
btd	p-value		0.888	0.887	0.885	0.026*
	t-statistic		0.14	-0.14	0.14	2.23
	coefficient		6.463275	-3.455404	4.031168	11.60817
tbd	p-value		0.488	0.174	0.126	0.000*
	t-statistic		-0.69	-1.36	1.53	-4.48
	coefficient		-106.2525	-110.1463	-0142.2445	-79.70631
pbd	p-value		0.488	0.174	0.126	0.000*
	t-statistic		-0.69	-1.35	1.53	-4.48
	coefficient		-10.62658	-11.02241	-14.22521	-7.967725
ts	p-value		0.926	0.526	0.699	0.435
	t-statistic		0.09	0.64	0.39	-0.78
	coefficient		13.26082	47.92244	33.61028	-12.33408
ocf	p-value		0.081	0.315	0.426	0.152
	t-statistic		-1.75	1.01	0.74	-1.43
	coefficient		-0.0886617	0.0281372	0.0235908	-0.113669
flvr	p-value		0.000*	0.001*	0.000*	0.000*
	t-statistic		-14.97	-3.36	-7.30	-18.51
	coefficient		-0.3049537	-0.0771574	-0.1616139	-1.652166
lnfa	p-value		0.11	0.062	0.979	0.000*
	t-statistic		1.61	-1.88	-0.03	6.19
	coefficient		0.0092339	-0.0160179	-0.0001993	.0102448
_cons	p-value		0.000	0.000	0.0000	0.000
	t-statistic		10.95	6.64	7.02	22.42
	Coefficient		0.2848017	0.2054517	0.2121882	.177882
R-Squared			57.67	0.2615	0.5479	0.3877
F-statistic (Prob)/ Wald chi2 (Prob)			35.93 (0.0000)	3.31(0.0015)	59.16 (0.0000)	38.06 (0.0000)
rho (fraction of variance due to u_i)				.87062491	.49943843	
Poolability Test (Breusch-Pagan LM)					340 (0.0000)	
Hausman test				129.44 (0.0000)		
Original Durbin-Watson statistic				2.04		
No of Observations = 220				Number of Firms = 20		

Dependent Variable: KCE, significant at *1%, **5%, t-statistics

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

We employed the *Multiple Regression, Correlated Panels Corrected Standard Errors (PCSEs) Model adjusted Autocorrelation (AR 1) statistics, Panel-level heteroskedastic and correlated across panels* to correct the positive first-order autocorrelation (ar1) as identified in the Wooldridge tests, multicollinearity as identified in the variance inflation factor and heteroskedasticity as indicated by the Breusch-Pagan test and Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian Multiplier test. The model also corrected the errors of variance due to differences across panels, that is, the intra-class correlation suggested by ρ (fraction of variance due to u_i) in the *Fixed Effects (FE) .8706 and Random Effects (RE) .4494 Models*.

From the statistics above, the R-squared (the multiple coefficients of determination) is 0.3877. In specific terms, it suggests that 38.77% of changes in total investment expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria can be explained by the regressors (*effective tax rate, book tax difference, temporary book tax difference, permanent book tax difference, tax savings, operating cash flows, financial leverage and natural logarithm of firm age*). However, the F-statistics = 38.06 and Prob. = 0.0000 are lower than = 0.05 which strengthens the overall statistical significance and reinforces the relevance of the predictors in the model. This also means that the 38.77% explanatory power of the regressors is statistically significant in explaining changes in the total investment expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria. Hence, this model is best fitted to explain the relationship between the regressors and the regressand included in the model.

Test of Hypotheses

Table 4.12: Multiple Regression, Correlated Panels Corrected Standard Errors (PCSEs) of Tax Sheltering Indicators and Corporate Investment Expenditure of Listed Financial Firms in Nigeria

Panel-corrected						
Variables	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf.	Interval]
Pbd	-1.224785	0.326608	-3.75	0.000	-1.864926	-0.584645
Ts	5.539032	2.768227	2.00	0.045	0.113408	10.964660
Ocf	0.000485	0.001346	0.36	0.718	-0.002152	0.003123
Flvr	-0.005318	0.000762	-6.98	0.000	-0.006812	-0.003824
Lnfa	0.001312	0.000253	5.18	0.000	0.000816	0.001809
_cons	0.006238	0.000903	6.91	0.000	0.004469	0.008008

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

Hypothesis one

H₀₁: Permanent book-tax difference has no significant effect on corporate investment expenditure of listed financial firms in Nigeria.

According to Gujarati, Porter, and Gunasekar (2009), the decision rule involves accepting the alternate hypothesis (H₁) if the coefficient for permanent book-tax difference (PBD) is either positive or negative, the modulus of the t-Statistic > 2.0, and the P-value of the t-Statistic < 0.05. Otherwise, accept H₀ and reject H₁.

Table 4.13 showed that the coefficient (β) of permanent book-tax difference is -1.22475, p-value = 0.000 and z-statistic = -3.75. The above results indicate that a unit change in the permanent book-tax difference will have an approximated inverse effect of -1.22 on the corporate investment expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria. Particularly, this variable displayed a very significant negative effect on the corporate investment expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria with a p-value = 0.000. Therefore, we accept the alternate hypothesis and conclude that corporate investment expenditure does react significantly to the changes in the permanent book-tax difference of the listed financial firms in Nigeria, since the p-value > 0.05 at 0.000, and t-statistic < |2| at -3.75.

Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Tax savings has no significant effect on corporate investment expenditure of listed financial firms in Nigeria.

Decision rule involves admitting the alternate hypothesis (H₁) if the coefficient for the tax savings (TS) is either positive or negative, the modulus of the t-Statistic > 2.0, (i.e. |t| > 2), and the P-value of

the t-Statistic < 0.05 (i.e. $|t| < 0.05$). Otherwise, accept H_0 and reject H_1 (Gujarati, Porter, and Gunasekar, 2009).

In respect of the coefficient (β), table 4.16 above indicates that a unit change in the tax savings will decrease the corporate investment expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria by 5.539031. Principally, this variable showcased a strong positive effect on the corporate investment expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria with a p-value = 0.045. Since the p-value > 0.05 at 0.045, and t-statistic $< |2|$ at 2.00, we accept the alternate hypothesis and conclude that tax savings has a significant effect on the corporate investment expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria.

5.0 CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Following the findings of the study, it was possible to conclude that the permanent *book-tax difference (PBD)* and *tax savings (TS)* are significant predictors of corporate investment expenditure of listed financial firms in Nigeria. The results also affirmed that *permanent book-tax difference (PBD)* have a negative significant effect on corporate investment expenditure which implies that corporate investment expenditure decreases as these indicators increases. From the results, there is clear evidence to conclude that *tax savings (TS)* is a direct predictor of corporate investment expenditure, that is, as tax savings increases. Based on the analysis results the following recommendations are derived from the findings:

- i. The financial firms in Nigeria should reduce the permanent book-tax difference in their books because it has been shown that as this gap is expanding, it adversely impacts of business growth opportunities through corporate investment expenditure.
- ii. Tax sheltering practices that encourage tax saving without widening the book-tax difference must be encouraged for optimal level of efficiency in tax savings because tax savings has proved to be a positive contributor to corporate investment expenditure.

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